

Non-Singular BCI-Algebras

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 29 December 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: DR. Md Najmul Hoda</p>	<p>The study of BCK/BCI algebras was initiated by Imai Iseki in 1966. These concepts of two classes of abstract algebras studied by eminent authors. Here we study properties of a non-singular BCI algebra which has been introduced by Prasad and Abid under the semi commutative BCI-algebra.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: BCI-algebra, Semi commutative BCI algebra and Non-singular BCI algebra etc.</p>	

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Definition (1.1) : A system $(X, *, 0)$ consisting of non-empty set X , a binary operation $*$ and fixed element 0 , is called a BCI-algebra if the following conditions are satisfied.

$$(BCI\ 1)\ ((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$$

$$(BCI\ 2)\ (x * (x * y)) * y = 0$$

$$(BCI\ 3)\ x * x = 0$$

$$(BCI\ 4)\ x * y = 0 = y * x \Rightarrow x = y$$

For all $x, y, z \in X$

Definition (1.2) : A BCI, algebra $(X, *, 0)$ is called

- (a) a BCK-algebra if $0 * x = 0$, for all $x \in X$
- (b) a non-singular BCI-algebra if $0 * x = x$ for all $x \in X$

Definition (1.3) : In a BCI-algebra, a partial ordering ' \leq ' is defined as $x \leq y$ iff $x * y = 0; x, y \in X$

Theorem (1.1) : Let $(X, *, 0)$ be a BCI-algebra. Then the following result hold

- (i) $x * 0 = x$
- (ii) $x * (x * (x * y)) = x * y$
- (iii) $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$
- (iv) $x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z$ and $z * y \leq z * x$

Definition (1.5) : A BCI – algebra is said to be

- (a) Commutative if $x * (x * y) = y * (y * x)$
- (b) Semi-commutative if $x * y = y * y$

For all $x, y \in X$

Proof : Let $x \neq y \neq 0$ and $x * y = 0$. Then the above theorem implies $y * x = 0$.

So condition (BCI 4) implies $x = y$. This is contradiction.

Hence $x * y \neq 0$

$$\text{Also } x * y = x \Rightarrow (x * y) * x = x * x.$$

$$\Rightarrow (x * x) * y = 0 \Rightarrow y = 0$$

which is also a contradiction.

$$\text{If } x * y = y \text{ then } y * x = y \Rightarrow (y * x) * y = y * y$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow (y * y) * x = 0 \\ &\Rightarrow x = 0 \end{aligned}$$

which is also a contradiction.

Hence the result

The above result very useful in providing example of non-singular BCI-algebra.

Theorem (1.2) : Let $(X, *, 0)$ be a non-singular BCI-algebras. Let a, b, c be three non-identical and non-zero element of X such that $a * b = c$ then $a * c = b$ and $b * c = a$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Proof : We have } a * c &= a * (a * b) \\ &= (a * b) * a = (a * a) * b \\ &= 0 * b = b \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Also } b * c &= b * (a * b) \\ &= (a * b) * b \\ &= (b * a) * b = (b * b) * a = 0 * a = a \end{aligned}$$

Corollary (1.1) : Every non-zero element of a non-singular BCI-algebra is an atom.

Proof : If $x * a = b$ Then the above theorem implies $x * b = a$. So $x * (x * a) = a$ for any $x \in X$ this proves that a is an atom of X .

Theorem (1.3) : In the binary table of a non-singular BCI-algebra no two elements of particular row (or a particular column) are identical.

Proof : Let $x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ be elements of a non singular BCI-algebra X . If possible suppose that $x_i * x_j = x_i * x_k$

Where $J \neq K$ then

$$\begin{aligned} (x_i * x_j) * x_i &= (x_j * x_k) * x_i \\ \Rightarrow (x_i * x_i) * x_j &= (x_i * x_i) * x_k \\ \Rightarrow 0 * x_j = 0 * x_k &\Rightarrow x_j = x_k \text{ which is contradiction. So no two} \\ &\text{elements of } i\text{th row are identical} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly we see that

$$x_i * x_1 = x_j * x_1 \ (i \neq j)$$

- $\Rightarrow (x_1 * x_i) * x_1 = (x_1 * x_j) * x_1$
- $\Rightarrow (x_1 * x_1) * x_i = (x_1 * x_1) * x_j$
- $\Rightarrow 0 * x_i = 0 * x_j$
- $\Rightarrow x_i = x_j$ which not true.

Hence the result.

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